

Work-Life Balance and Employees of Corporate Sector of Pakistan

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Dua Shaikh**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: duashaikh123@hotmail.com

⁽²⁾ **Dr. Masood Hassan**

PhD, IoBM, Karachi, Pakistan and Visiting Faculty Greenwich, Karachi, Pakistan,

Email: masoodhassan1@hotmail.com (**Corresponding Author**)

⁽³⁾ **Abdul Moiz Dawra**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: dawra1998@gmail.com

Abstract:

The core objective of this research is to identify the impact that a healthy work-life balance brings to the corporate sector of Pakistan. To help the employees identify the impact that this can bring to their respective organizations A healthy work-life balance makes employees more productive. Being productive means work being completed more timely, more effort being put into it to make sure it is accurate and up-to-the-mark. This works in the best favor of the corporates as well since it makes employees more motivated. With being productive, employees become more satisfied too with their respective jobs. A satisfied employee will not hunt for other jobs and will be content with the current jobs, which again, benefits the corporates, since they get to retain their hard-working and well-trained employees and business policies and secrets are remained safe within the business as employees will be more loyal to their employers.

Keywords: *Work-life balance, Corporate sector, Job Productivity, Job Satisfaction, Employee Retention*

Introduction

Work-life balance means having satisfaction with one's entire life, at work and home. Work-life balance refers to the process of separating one's professional and personal lives such that neither interferes with the other. The concept does not mean having equal time given at work and home, trying to schedule an equal time to work and personal life is unrealistic and unattainable. This balance keeps on changing through the course of one's life, depending upon what your work and personal life require from you at that specific time. It is important to understand that for everyone work and personal life hold different priorities so it should not be enforced as a generalized rule (Cameron, 2021).

Work-life (im)balance is highly influenced by the type of job, project-based work, and industry. Project-based work, for example, with its unpredictable work pressure and requirement to finish projects on schedule on a regular basis, usually entails extensive travel, which can strain family connections. Longer work hours and work outside of regular hours at the expense of family and home time, when paired with heavy workloads pressure, and stress, can lead to poor health, tension, anxiety, exhaustion, and other deleterious psycho-physiological repercussions, all of which can negatively impact family and work-life quality (Chiang et al., 2010).

The idea that a person's job puts them under a great deal of stress, they have high expectations, and there are no work-life balance regulations and norms have also been documented in the literature. Job needs, dedication and devotion, cultural beliefs, and change are some of the challenges that prevent firms from implementing work-life balance rules. Work demands are likely to be substantially connected with work-to-family conflicts, which can be of two types: time-based and strain-based, according to Voydanoff (2004). Long paid working hours limit the amount of time a person may spend with friends and family.

Employees may find it challenging to maintain family relationships and conduct family-oriented tasks or activities due to a lack of time. Job insecurity or worry of losing a job can sometimes threaten the economic well-being necessary for life quality and stability. Stress caused by work uncertainty reduces interpersonal availability and makes it difficult to participate fully in family life. Family commitments can sometimes make it

difficult for a person to execute his or her job efficiently, the fact that research has focused on conflict is associated with work-life rather than family-work conflict, (Cho et al., 2010).

Employees in the corporate sector of Pakistan, specifically those with office jobs have work timings from 9 am to 5 pm. Those 8 hours should be as productive as possible without overburdening the employees. To make sure this happening, it is crucial that the employee is coming to work stress-free and can manage the duties that are assigned to them. Staying in late to work and working additional hours at home is the prime example of a disruptive work-life balance. It is supposed that working more will increase productivity when in reality it will only decrease performance per employee as the employee will not be satisfied with their job (Meenakshi et al., 2013).

We have a lot of multinationals operating in Pakistan and the success rate of these is also substantial. The reason for this success is that they strive for employee retention; they do this by creating a happy work environment for their employees, not overburdening them, and providing fringe benefits to gain employees' job satisfaction. It is important to take these businesses as an example when referring to overall business success (Rehman & Siddiqui, 2019).

A prime reason for business failure could be that their employees are not satisfied with their job, they do not provide that space to their employees have a work-life balance, which result contributes to employees looking for other jobs and the business losing their assets i.e. their employees (Naseem et al., 2011).

Work-life Balance

The concept was coined in early-1986, but its usage and exposure were still not normalized until several years later. Even though the work-life balance programs were witnessed in the 1930s, however, its meaning wasn't clear to the people of the time. Before WWII, the W.K. Kellogg Company developed some degree of work-hour flexibility, old working hours were replaced, and results were determined. The new, flexible working hours proved successful in providing job satisfaction and improved rate of efficiency and productivity among employees (Isaacs, 2016).

Rosabeth Moss Kanter, in her landmark book *Family and Work in the United States: A Critical Review and Agenda for Research and Policy*, published in 1977, emphasized this topic for the first time and advocated that it be practiced more regularly everywhere. Therefore, in the 1980s and 1990s, some companies were noticed to bring this practice forward. The first attempt at these programs going viral was mostly for women who had children to take care of (Ahuja, 2020).

Literature has reviewed that the concept that this phenomenon entails is worth discussion as it provides a framework for a balance in work-life. Numerous studies have discussed that work-life programs offer a win-win situation to not just the employees of an organization, but the employers as well, and it also provides the organization with a competitive advantage which helps improve work-life balance practices which increase productivity, the well-being of employees, cost reduction, leads to employee retention and a more encourages and motivated work environment (Cole, 2019).

This notion of work-life balance should become a focal point of focus in every business, not simply the corporate one. Every little or big size organization, whether it be government systems, research institutes, people, or trade unions. Work-life balance is an important constituent of human resource management which means giving your employees the liberty to combine work and life in a way that one does not overwhelm the other (Ahuja, 2020).

Work-life balance encompasses these factors: Managing time, tolerable pressure, job satisfaction, job stress, commitment to the organization, satisfaction with one's life, employee turnover, welfare, being socially secured, time allotted to work, being flexible with work, family being a priority too, (un)employment, consumption, demographic changes, personal space and the list goes on. In this paper, work is defined as paid work i.e. a person gets paid for working for/providing services to an organization (Murphy, 2006).

"It's impossible to strike a work-life balance." "You make work-life decisions, and they have repercussions," said Jack Welch, the former CEO of General Electric and all-around business genius. Work and family are the two most important aspects of a person's life, and finding a balance between them has become a major problem for scholars all over the world (Khallash & Kruse, 2012).

Working couples, the only families, globalization, highs and lows in labor demand, a rise in parents who are responsible for the child, spouses, and/or spouses' families, a rise in the number of working women, and aging parents have all combined to form the having to work on work-life balance. It is crucial to put a balance between too, otherwise, it results in not being able to prioritize family or leisure time and if one does prioritize it then is too overburdened with work, and the day's tiredness and fatigue hinders being able to spend a normal and comfortable life (Todd & Binns, 2011).

Another factor to this issue is that an employee who is overburdened with work may never be able to have a healthy pattern of life. Burden invited stress and stress if not dealt with properly can hinder not just work but may result in declining health. With poor concentration levels at work, an employee is not able to provide the productivity levels that his/her job requires from them. This not just puts that employee on the verge of losing their job but also harms the organization (Ravenswood & Harris, 2016).

Stress is considered to be the biggest threat in disrupting one's personal and professional life, you lose concentration, you get agitated, productivity is declining, etc. These employees then expect their employers to understand that they have a life outside of work and that overwhelming work stress is practically making them lose their sanity over time. Studies have shown that a life with no balance results in a poorer standard of living having issues with work-life is considered to be the main reason why some employees quit their jobs (Grzywacz & Carlson, 2007).

Researchers all around the world are focusing more on the link between family and work balance, as well as the benefits of this idea, which is known as work-life facilitation. This facilitation is witnessed when one domain impacts or improves another domain. Organizations are encouraged to force their HR departments to make policies that positively influence work-life balance, which in turn proves to be beneficial for not just the employees but the organizations too (Issac, 2017).

Measures are taken to ensure Work-Life balance help improve job productivity and help organizations retain their employees which reduces employee turnover, which in turn reduces employee-employer feuds and other employee-related problems (Ramadoss & Lape, 2014).

In addition to this, because this helps organizations in retaining their loyal employees it also saves the organizations from losing their employees to their competitors who can extort the organizations' information, reduces training and recruitment costs and employees will be more satisfied with their jobs and wouldn't require taking off from work, good quality of the workforce, reduced work stress, high self-esteem, helps to boost confidence and loyalty to the business Employers may profit from this in terms of increased labor availability, loyal workers, long-term employee-employer relationships, high employee participation, and favorable employee motivation and behavior (Beauregard & Henry, 2009).

Job Satisfaction

The millennial generation has produced employees that are more flexible and require a flexible environment to work in. As a result, one of the most important things that are a basic demand of the mentioned set of individuals in a firm is work-life balance. "Job satisfaction is an employee's assessment of his or her job to determine how well the organization has met their expectations" (Silaban & Margaretha, 2021).

Work-life balance provides job satisfaction and helps employees stay more focused, they should have enough time of their own to keep their personal and professional life out of each other. Due to a drastic increase in globalization, organizations have become more and more competitive, and economic growth has been seen to increase as well. "The human resources engaged in it must have been able to participate, endure, and win the competition," says the company (Ganapathi, 2016).

To achieve these growth targets, companies have become more versatile and understanding in terms of providing work-life balance space to their employees. This has gauged a satisfied workforce that is much more loyal to the company and provides great outcomes for the business (Ziegler et al., 2012).

Big companies in Pakistan, such as Engro, provide healthcare not just for their employees but also for the families of their employees. This puts the employee out of stress to provide health care for their families and makes them more focused on their work as well, and a healthy amount of time is spent with their families as well. These employees don't have to do multiple jobs or take more work from their existing job to pay the bills for hospitals. This is intent to provide a healthy work and personal environment to their employees that Engro is seen to have implemented (Wnuk, 2017).

By bringing work-life balance programs into the corporate sector, employees will have more to do than just constantly working like machines. Humans need breaks to keep up with their concentration levels which are lost if over-burdened, thus, making them feel dissatisfied and agitated. This will encourage employees to have a life outside of their work, by spending time with a loved one, investing time in self-care such as going to the gym, or relaxing on a weekend, instead of working weekends as well, therefore it creates a balance that will make employees happier and more satisfied to do their work-life (Cakmur, 2011).

Employees that are unsatisfied with their occupations will never be psychologically content, and will eventually demonstrate negative attitudes or behaviors at work, which might lead to unhappiness. Employees who are happy with their employment, on the other hand, will work even harder, more enthusiastically, and more active than those who are unhappy with their positions (Yahya & Khadeer, 2021).

Possibilities for advancement, job security, compensation, company and leadership, supervision, workplace environment, social parts of the work, and facilities are some of the factors that influence job happiness, according to Sutrisno (2017).

Employee job happiness is crucial for the company's survival since happy employees have a positive influence on the company, such as greater efficiency and production (Kanwar et al., 2009). Employees will feel more satisfied working for the firm and will be more productive if they have a good work-life balance (Dahlan, 2016).

Workplace issues like the pressure of work, longer working hours, harassment, etc can be addressed through a wide range of HR interventions and employee satisfaction strategies like flextime, job rotation, job growth, family get-togethers, kids school funds, and child care centers, among many others, which will motivate employees by making them committed to their jobs and give their all Person et al. (2010).

Job Productivity

Throughout the pandemic, the concept of work-life balance developed as one of the most pressing workplace challenges, especially as the world moved toward remote employment. Organizations faced serious productivity and mental health issues as a result of competing family duties, transitioning to working from home, and job creeps. Employees and businesses alike sought to establish a happy medium that suited everyone (Rouse et al., 1978).

Insomnia rates, for example, were cited as a surrogate for poor work balance and workplace stress, suggesting that people were suffering and that businesses and employees needed to pay more attention to this balance. Employees are just people, and your human capital determines your productivity. With all this in mind, here are among the most significant ways that a work-life balance affects workplace productivity (Oluwasola, 2015).

When employees have a healthy work-life balance, they are more motivated to take on office responsibilities. A good balance will help them feel invigorated, and because there will be less stress and worry at work, it will be simpler for them to complete their office chores. Because there are so many other things to live for, there is a greater desire and passion to confront the job. Employees that are motivated are more productive and efficient (Mukoyama, 2013).

He or she comes to work with a positive attitude, which typically spreads across the office. Work-life balance is thus something to promote because it is a self-sustaining productivity booster. It should, as usual, begin at the top and work its way down. Leaders must mainstream and legitimize their actions (Gentle, 2021).

Higher levels of stress have historically been linked to lower productivity. Cortisol levels rise when you're stressed, affecting your work effectiveness. Your failure to finish all of the tasks set for each day, despite the stress you place on yourself, will lead you to come to a complete halt, lack trust, and leave terrible images on your coworkers, all of which will lead to you despising your job and, as a consequence, productivity will suffer. As a business owner, that will be the last thing you would like from your employees (Lee & Qu, 2019).

Sparks, Cooper, Fried, and Shirom, (1997) in their study provide, that a healthy work-life balance allows people to take time off from work to satisfy personal obligations, and vice versa. As a consequence, the anxiety and stress that your workers experience as a result of having to continuously put one aspect of their lives along for the other are reduced. People often need to be shown how to restore their work-life balance since they have been accustomed to working excessively and ignoring other aspects of their lives.

When employees have a positive work balance, they are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs, their bosses, and their coworkers. This is for obvious reasons: you will feel much better about work if it isn't your sole activity. This can be said about a lot of things in life. The term "balance" refers to the ability to put things into perspective. At its most basic level, work-life balance is avoiding sacrificing one's personal life for professional responsibilities. It's not always easy to achieve, and it frequently necessitates difficult dialogues with oneself and, in some cases, one's workplace (Martin et al., 2022).

There are several approaches to accomplishing this, and it means various things to different individuals. Some of us are far more resistant to the development of stress and the consequent decreases in productivity than others. Others have family obligations that need a healthy work-life balance, but they rapidly succumb when their personal lives are put on hold in favor of nonstop work. Encourage work-life balance as an element of your productivity-boosting arsenal as a manager, realizing that when people live richer lives, they have more energy (Shobe, 2018).

You will despise that one thing if you believe that all you have to worry about and look forward to is the usual old office routine, which comes at the expense of your interpersonal relationships, hobbies, and even just time spent standing still while doing nothing (Oden, 2021)

Employee Retention

Employee retention, as per (S et al., 2019), is a measure of a company's ability to keep its employees. It's also recognized as a procedure in which employees are motivated and advised to keep with a firm for a longer period to secure its long-term survival. In many service-oriented organizations, employee salaries are the largest and most expensive part of the budget.

When a person leaves, the costs of turnover are substantial, from the time it takes to remarket, interview, and offer the position to the problems of training someone on how to use your systems. Work-life balance is now becoming a crucial motivation for companies who want to retain their staff for longer periods. According to CompareCamp, companies with good work-life balance policies have a 25% higher employee retention rate. This corresponds to cost savings in terms of training and recruitment (Gupta, 2004).

According to most research, the longer your staff works the less new productivity they acquire from each hour after that. While they may do excellent work over the first 40 hours, hours 41-50 are less successful, and hours 51 and beyond are significantly less effective. While certain sectors require teams to be available 24 hours a day, many more organizations may use solutions that allow employees to avoid 2 a.m. phone calls or 12-hour workdays. More businesses are attempting to establish cultures in which "presenteeism" isn't the criterion for success, but rather the accuracy and timeliness of the product (Yadav, 2020).

Many new opportunities for firms ready to innovate arise as a result of this emphasis on work-life balance while working from home. Even if your company has traditionally had a reputation of working late to get things done,

you may find that you can no longer retain personnel in this manner. People increasingly desire time away from work to pursue other interests (Singh, 2018).

Employees with families also want to spend more time with their spouses and children all while sharing domestic responsibilities. According to research, beyond a certain level of money, happiness does not grow much for every new dollar of income. Instead, astute employers are learning that making work more enjoyable might help them retain their best employees (Stieg, 2021).

Even when senior management sincerely wants its contributors to have a work-life balance, the majority of high-competence team members will follow the C-lead. Expect ambitious staff to work till 9 p.m. if the company's owner does. Visibility is crucial. While a CEO may prefer to spend a holiday period with his family, making it very clear that he'd rather only be checking business email once or twice a day during those vacations might send an essential message to staff (Dwiedienawati, 2020).

Top management is also where the true change in the world of structure vs chaos may take place. To overcome difficulties in chaotic work situations, people prefer to rely upon last hard labor. When unexpected demands arise in a well-organized workplace, higher management asks, "What should we do to avoid it the next time?" If your present workplace systems routinely demand long hours, unexpected work weekends, and on-call presence to address concerns that should have been resolved sooner, you may need a new platform to assist you to avoid these habits (Tangthong et al., 2014).

Conclusion

Work-life balance however difficult to manage and achieve remains the crucial factor in determining a favorable outcome for not just the employees, but also the corporates. Based on the arguments presented in this paper, and the research carried out, it shows that without a sustained work-life balance, employees were not satisfied with their jobs, and they were not productive enough, which resulted in corporates losing their important assets i.e. their employees. Over-burdened with work that is stressful can not only drive employees to mess up the work they have been assigned, but also will produce a declining mental health, which will make them frustrated and agitated at all times. This will result in ruining their personal and professional relationships which will deprive the employee from maintaining any positivity in their lives. A healthy work-life balance makes employee want to work more efficiently and effectively, makes them more focused, which works in the best interest of the corporates as well since employees are more motivated to provide better results. They are less stressed and more mentally and physically equipped to carry out the tasks assigned. The last thing corporates want is to lose their well-trained, hardworking employees, and this is exactly what is happening when the employee feels too over-worked and constantly under-pressure. Corporates spend millions on training their employees, and the time taken to train these employees, that could be spent doing other important tasks is also a lot, and when such employees leave the companies have to face a lot of issues. To make sure this doesn't happen, it should be made sure that work-life policies are implemented.

References.

- Ahuja, S. (2020). Life Chakra Mantra for Work-Life Balance. *International Journal Of Food, Nutrition & Dietetics*, 8(1), 9-13. <https://doi.org/10.21088/ijfnd.2322.0775.8120.1>
- Aziz-Ur-Rehman, M. and Siddiqui, D., 2019. Relationship between Flexible Working Arrangements and Job Satisfaction Mediated by Work-Life Balance: Evidence from Public Sector Universities Employees of Pakistan. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
- Beauregard, T.A., & Henry, L.C. (2009). Linking work-life balance practices and organizational performance. *Human Resource Management Review*, 19, 9-22.
- Cakmur, H. (2011). Concept and Evaluation of Job Satisfaction: Developed Job Satisfaction Index. *TAF Preventive Medicine Bulletin*, 10(6), 759. <https://doi.org/10.5455/pmb.20111018014747>

- Cameron, M. (2021, February 18). The Importance of Work-Life Balance. Sprig HR. <https://sprigghr.com/blog/performance-culture/the-importance-of-work-life-balance/#:%7E:text=Work-life%20balance%20helps%20maintain%20mental%20health%20Having%20a,burnout%2C%20two%20common%20health%20issues%20in%20the%20workplace.>
- Cho, S. S., Ko, J. H., Pellecchia, G., van Eimeren, T., Cilia, R., & Strafella, A. P. (2010). Continuous theta-burst stimulation of the right dorsolateral prefrontal cortex induces changes in impulsivity levels. *Brain Stimulation*, 3(3), 170–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brs.2009.10.002>
- Cole, M. (2019, April 19). Mark Cole: Leadership Seasons. John Maxwell. <https://www.johnmaxwell.com/blog/tag/work-life-balance/>
- D, V., S, K., & J, K. (2019). Employee Retention Techniques. *Journal Of Research On The Lepidoptera*, 50(1), 40-47. <https://doi.org/10.36872/lepi/v50i1/201055>
- Dwiedienawati, D. (2020). Transformational Leadership, Communication Quality Influences to Perceived Organization Effectiveness and Employee Engagement and Employee Retention during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal Of Advanced Research In Dynamical And Control Systems*, 12(SP7), 773-787. <https://doi.org/10.5373/jardcs/v12sp7/20202169>
- G. Grzywacz, J., & S. Carlson, D. (2007). Just a moment Sagepub.Com. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1523422307305487>
- Gentle, S. (2021). How Having a Work-Life Balance Affects Workplace Productivity | Onrec. Onrec.Com. <https://www.onrec.com/news/news-archive/how-having-a-work-life-balance-affects-workplace-productivity>
- Gupta, S. (2004). Employee Retention. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.640430>
- Isaacs, D. (2016). Work-life balance. *Journal Of Paediatrics And Child Health*, 52(1), 5-6. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpc.13110>
- Khallash, S., & Kruse, M. (2012). The Future of Work and Work-Life Balance 2025. *Futures*, 44, 678-686. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2012.04.007>
- Lee, J., & Qu, Q. (2019). The Effects of Person-Job Mismatch on the Intrinsic Job Satisfaction. *Productivity Review*, 33(4), 167-210. <https://doi.org/10.15843/kpapr.33.4.2019.12.167>
- Martin, L., Hauret, L., & Fuhrer, C. (2022). Digitally transformed home office impacts job satisfaction, job stress, and job productivity. COVID-19 findings. *PLOS ONE*, 17(3), e0265131. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0265131>
- Meenakshi, M. S. P., Subrahmanyam C. V, M. V., & Ravichandran, D. K. (2013). IOSR Journal. [Www.Iosrjournals.Org](http://www.iosrjournals.org/). Retrieved 2013, from <https://www.iosrjournals.org/>
- Mukoyama, T. (2013). The Cyclicity of Job-to-Job Transitions and Its Implications for Aggregate Productivity. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2244488>
- Murphy, L. (2006). Work-Life Balance – A Psychological Perspective Fiona Jones Work-Life Balance – A Psychological Perspective et al (Eds) Psychology Press 320pp£39.99 18416952971841695297. *Nursing Standard*, 20(39), 36-36. <https://doi.org/10.7748/ns.20.39.36.s39>
- Naseem, A., Sheikh, S. E., & P. Malik, P. K. (2011). Impact of Employee Satisfaction on Success of Organization: Relation between Customer Experience and Employee Satisfaction. [Www.Ijmse.Org](http://www.ijmse.org/). <http://www.ijmse.org/Volume2/Issue5/paper8.pdf>
- Oden, C. (2021). Cloudflare. [Projecttopics.Org](https://www.projecttopics.org/work-life-balancing-effect-employee-productivity.html). <https://www.projecttopics.org/work-life-balancing-effect-employee-productivity.html>
- Oluwasola, A. K. (2015, July 17). Work-Life balance and employee productivity. Academia. Uk. https://www.academia.edu/12974883/Work-Life_balance_and_employee_productivity
- Pathak, Abhishek & Dubey, Pushkar & Singh, Deepak. (2019). Work-Life Balance & Job Satisfaction: A Literature Review. *International journal of computer sciences and engineering*. 7. 182-187. 10.6084/m9.figshare.12016704.

- Ramadoss, K., & E. Lape, M. (2014). Supervisor Status, Health, and Organizational Commitment: Mediating Role of Support and Family-friendly Policies among Information Technology Professionals in India. *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 2(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.12691/jbms-2-1-1>
- Ravenswood, K., & Harris, C. (2016). Doing Gender, Paying Low: Gender, Class and Work-Life Balance in Aged Care. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 23(6), 614-628. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gwao.12149>
- Rouse, J., Katzell, R., & Yankelovich, D. (1978). Work, Productivity, and Job Satisfaction. *Public Productivity Review*, 3(1), 86. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3379936>
- S, J., R, V., & G, S. K. (2019). A Study on Employee Retention. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 11(0009-SPECIAL ISSUE), 1315–1319. <https://doi.org/10.5373/jardcs/v11/20192742>
- Shobe, K. (2018). Productivity Driven by Job Satisfaction, Physical Work Environment, Management Support, and Job Autonomy. *Business And Economics Journal*, 09(02). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2151-6219.1000351>
- Silaban, H., & Margaretha, M. (2021). The Impact Work-Life Balance toward Job Satisfaction and Employee Retention: Study of Millennial Employees in Bandung City, Indonesia. *International Journal of Innovation and Economic Development*, 7(3), 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.18775/ijied.1849-7551-7020.2015.73.2002>
- Singh, H. (2018). Determinants of Employee Retention in an Organization: An Empirical Investigation. *Journal Of Advances And Scholarly Researches In Allied Education*, 15(3), 140-143. <https://doi.org/10.29070/15/57322>
- Stieg, C. (2021, January 12). From the “perfect” salary to keeping up with the Joneses, here’s how money affects your happiness. CNBC. <https://www.cnbc.com/2020/05/26/how-your-salary-and-the-way-you-spend-money-affect-your-happiness.html>
- Tangthong, S., Trimetsoontorn, J., & Rojniruntikul, N. (2014). HRM Practices and Employee Retention in Thailand—A Literature Review. *International Journal Of Trade, Economics, And Finance*, 5(2), 162-166. <https://doi.org/10.7763/ijtef.2014.v5.362>
- Todd, P., & Binns, J. (2011). Work-life Balance: Is it Now a Problem for Management?. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 20(3), 219-231. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0432.2011.00564.x>
- Wnuk, M. (2017). Organizational Conditioning of Job Satisfaction. A Model of Job Satisfaction. *Contemporary Economics*, 11(1), 31-44. <https://doi.org/10.5709/ce.1897-9254.227>
- Yadav, A. (2020). Employee Retention and Employee Engagement. *International Journal Of Management*, 08(02), 47-52. <https://doi.org/10.35620/ijm.2020.8202>
- Yahya, K. W., & Khadeer, E. E. (2021). Study the Effect of Weight Fractions of Different Powders on the Attenuation Performances of the Epoxy Composite. *NeuroQuantology*, 19(9), 142–151. <https://doi.org/10.14704/nq.2021.19.9.nq21147>
- Ziegler, R., Hagen, B., & Diehel, M. (2012). Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Job Performance: Job Ambivalence as a Moderator. *Journal Of Applied Social Psychology*, 42(8), 2019-2040. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.2012.00929.x>